

A NEW GROUP OF COLLOIDAL ELECTROLYTES

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Some of the sols, e.g. silicic acid, vanadic acid, tungstic acid, molybdic acid, telluric acid, and antimonie acid which can be coagulated by electrolytes either in the absence of alkali or by the addition of traces of alkali, which makes them unstable towards coagulation, show high electric conductivity. In all these sols a part of the substance exists in the molecular condition and another part as polymerised molecules, capable of giving out complex ions, which are readily adsorbed by the sol particles.

On dilution, simple molecules in the dissolved condition are produced from the polymerised and colloidal aggregates and thus the electrical conductivity increases with dilution. All these properties show that these substances are typical colloidal electrolytes.

Soaps, silicates, several dyestuffs, alkaline and acidic proteins, etc. are now considered as colloidal electrolytes. In this paper we are advancing evidence in favour of the view that silicic, vanadic, tungstic, molybdic, telluric and antimonie acids may be included in the category of colloidal electrolytes. Some of these conduct electricity fairly well and all of them behave as colloids.

Stability as Colloids

We have investigated the coagulation of sols by potassium chloride in presence or absence of small amounts of alkali and the following results are obtained.

TABLE I

Sols of acids.	Precipitation value of KCl without alkali.	with alkali.	Amount of alkali added.
Silicic	—	0'000M	KOH 0'0271M
Vanadic	0'0229M	0'0064	NH ₄ OH 0'0133
Tungstic	0'0354	0'0125	KOH 0'0097
Molybdic	0'3300	0'1800	NH ₄ OH 0'0160
Telluric	0'2800	0'0800	NaOH 0'0833

We have advanced the view in previous publications that the sols are composed of a certain amount of the substance in true molecular condition in the dissolved state existing as simple and polymerised molecules and the following equilibrium is likely to exist:—

The electric charge on the colloid particles is chiefly due to the adsorption of x polymerised anions carrying n units of electric charge and y simple anions each carrying one unit charge. The adsorption of the complex ions appear to be more important than that of the simple anions in the formation of the sol because of the greater amount of electric charge carried by the complex anions. The above view point is supported by the fact that small amounts of alkali render the sols unstable towards KCl although all of them are negatively charged. This behaviour is entirely different from that of sols like ferric hydroxide, chromium hydroxide, etc., which when prepared under ordinary conditions, are positively charged and they are rendered stable by the addition of H⁺ ions. This peculiar behaviour of the negatively charged sols of silicic, vanadic, tungstic acids etc. has been explained by us in the following manner: when an alkali is added to such a sol, it reacts with the simple molecules first and in order to restore the equilibrium more of the simple

molecules are formed at the expense of the polymerised ones which give out complex negative ions. These negative complex ions are more responsible for the stabilisation of the sols than the simpler ions and as the alkali causes the removal of the complex anions, the sols are rendered unstable in their presence as shown in Table I. On the other hand, in presence of acids these sols are likely to be more stable as was shown by Schulz and Jander (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 162, 141) in the case of tungstic acid sol and by us in the case of vanadic acid sol.

Electrical Conductivity and other Properties of the Colloids

Silicic Acid Sol.—Mylius and Groschuff (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 116) conclude that at the moment of formation of silicic acid by the action of acids on water glass, it exists in the molecular condition, which passes unchanged through a parchment dialyser. Colloidal particles then result from the polymerisation of the simple silicic acid molecules on keeping the solution and this is shown by the increase of molecular weight for many weeks. Several workers have concluded that this ageing process leads to the formation of highly polymerised colloid particles and finally to crystalline silica. We have also come to the same conclusion from our observation that silicic acid sol develops a marked increase in viscosity with time. It is generally believed that in the process of coagulation of sols there is an aggregation of colloidal particles and in this process there is usually an increase in their viscosity.

We have also investigated the change in the electrical conductivity of a dialysed sol of silicic acid (prepared by the hydrolysis of silicon tetrachloride) with time and the following results have been obtained.

TABLE II

Sol conc. = 6.17g. of SiO_2 /litre. Temp. = 30°

Date	... 4-4-1927	2-5-1927
Specific conductivity	... 5.75×10^{-8}	6.10×10^{-8}

Tungstic Acid Sol.—This sol, obtained according to the method of Graham by adding an acid to sodium tungstate solution, rapidly passes through a parchment paper and it is well known that this optically clear sol contains a large percentage of the acid in the molecular state. We prepared tungstic acid sol by first precipitating the substance by the action of an excess of hydrochloric acid on sodium tungstate at 8° and the sodium chloride and the excess of hydrochloric acid removed by washing the precipitate, which gradually passed into a sol. The sol was further purified by dialysis, when some tungstic acid appeared in the dialysate. The pure sol, free from chloride ions, was found still to contain appreciable amounts of tungstic acid, which did not coagulate by electrolytes like KCl, KNO_3 , etc. The electrical conductivity of the sol was fairly high and it was distinctly acidic (H^+ ion conc. = 10^{-3}). The influence of ageing on the electric conductivity was also determined and the following results were obtained.

TABLE III

Date	... 22-10-1927	31-10-1927	2-11-1927	4-11-1927	18-11-1927
Sp. conductivity. $\times 10^8$	... 4.12	3.883	3.769	3.728	3.632

The equivalent conductivity of tungstic acid was determined by Sobolew (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, 12, 169) and the following are his results,

TABLE IV

Temp. = 24°

ν	...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ	...	176.4	233.5	279.1	325.1	371.6	416.7

These results prove that an appreciable amount of tungstic acid remains in the dissolved condition as simple and polymerised molecules, which dissociate into hydrogen ions and a negative ion. A decrease in the specific conductivity on ageing is obviously due to the formation of more of polymerised molecules and the colloidal aggregates with time.

Molybdic Acid Sol—Rosenheim and Bertheim (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 36, 427) have reported that the dihydrate of molybdenum trioxide has a definite solubility and the acid diffuses through a parchment paper and possesses the molecular weight of 600. We have carefully studied this sol obtained by the interaction of hydrochloric acid and ammonium molybdate. As the sol is allowed to dialyse, a large percentage of the molybdic acid passes through the parchment paper. With time the portion of the acid existing as simple molecules gradually polymerises and finally forms colloid aggregates as will be evident from the following results on the ultrafiltration of the sol obtained by us.

TABLE V

MoO₃ in 100 c.c of the sol = 1.550 g.

Time (hr.)	...	...	...	2	24	48	72	96	120
MoO ₃ in 100 c.c of the filtrate (g.)	...	...	...	0.740	0.732	0.726	0.714	0.706	0.700
MoO ₃ as colloid in 100 c.c of the sol (g.)	...	...	...	0.810	0.818	0.824	0.832	0.840	0.846
% present as colloid. ...	...	...	...	52.1	52.77	53.16	53.67	54.19	54.59

In Table VI the results are recorded to show considerable diminution of percentage of the colloid on dilution of the sol.

TABLE VI

Sol. conc.	MoO ₃ in 100 c.c of the		MoO ₃ as colloid in 100 c.c. of the sol.	% of colloid.
	sol.	filtrate.		
2%	1.55 g.	0.740 g.	0.810 g	52.2
1	0.775	0.508	0.267	34.4
0.5	0.3875	0.296	0.0915	23.9

A dialysed sol of molybdic acid and freed from the impurities shows an appreciable electrical conductivity and distinct acidity which decrease with time (Table VII).

TABLE VII

Date	...	27-12-28	31-12-28	4-1-29
Sp. condy. at 30° × 10 ³	...	1.719	1.676	1.660

The following results were obtained by Grossmann and Krämer (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1606) on the molecular conductivity of a solution of dihydrated molybdenum trioxide.

TABLE VIII

ν	...	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ	...	95.8	129.5	147.5	155.6	160.6	163.6	169.6

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.—Several years ago Dumanaski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 147) showed that the composition of the colloidal aggregates of vanadium pentoxide sol has the formula of $[H_2V_2O_7(V_2O_5)_2]^{10}$. We have found that an appreciable amount of vanadic acid is present in the molecular state in a sol of vanadium pentoxide, which cannot be precipitated by an electrolyte and that this amount decreases appreciably with time.

The electrical conductivity of a dialysed vanadium pentoxide sol decreases with the ageing of the sol as given in the following table.

TABLE IX

Sol conc. = $M/180$.

Date	...	...	10-4-22	9-5-22	22-6-22	9-9-22
Mol conductivity at 30°	...	...	113.4	91.5	85.1	83.8

Vanadium pentoxide sol, therefore, shows a high electrical conductivity and contains some of the substance in the dissolved state, which gives out ions. The simple molecules gradually aggregate forming polymerised molecules and finally polymerised molecules form still larger aggregates producing the particles of colloidal dimension.

Telluric Acid.—Rosenheim and Jander (*Kolloid Z.*, 1918, 22, 23) have concluded that a solution of telluric acid behaves as a semi-colloid. We have investigated the colloidal property of this acid and have found that the acid is not coagulated by such electrolytes as KCl, NaCl, LiCl, RbCl etc. but the sol becomes unstable and can be coagulated by these electrolytes in the presence of traces of an alkali. These results are analogous to the behaviour of a silicic acid sol. Similarly Behren and Traube (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 146, 1) have reported on the colloidal behaviour of telluric acid. Moreover, irregularities in the boiling point measurement indicate the formation of some colloidal telluric acid.

We have observed that on dialysis practically all telluric acid passes through the parchment paper and this is due to the fact that the tendency of this acid to form simpler products is very prominent with dilution.

Rosen and Jander (*loc cit.*) have determined the electrical conductivity of telluric acid at 30° and their results are reproduced below.

TABLE X

ν	...	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ	...	0.1902	0.1984	0.2029	0.2119	0.2245	0.2611	0.3131	0.4460	0.6913

The electrical conductivity of H_2S is greater than that of telluric acid, which is weaker than H_2S as an acid.

We have also studied the change in the electrical conductivity of the sol of telluric acid with time and the following are our results.

TABLE XI

Conc. of telluric acid = 100 g./litre.

Time (days)	...	...	5	10
Sp. conductivity $\times 10^4$	...	...	0.773	0.775

The hydrogen ion concentration of 100 g. of the sol per litre is $10^{-11.5}$ showing that it is a very weak acid.

Antimonic Acid Sol.—Delacroix (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1899, *iii*, 21, 1049), and Senderens (*ibid.*, p. 47) believed that the product obtained by the hydrolysis of antimony pentachloride existed in the state of true solution. Jander (*Kolloid Z.*, 1918, 23, 1822) reported it to be a semi-colloid. We have studied the colloidal behaviour of antimonic acid obtained by first precipitating antimonic acid from potassium antimonate by nitric acid and then peptising the sol by washing off the electrolytes. The sol was further purified by dialysis when a slightly turbid negatively charged sol of antimonic acid was obtained. A considerable amount of antimonic acid passed out through a parchment paper and some acid, which cannot be coagulated by electrolytes like KCl, KNO₃, etc., remained showing that a certain amount of this acid exists in the molecular form. We have also shown that the acid remaining in the molecular form consists mostly of simple molecules. Hence the sol does not become appreciably unstable by traces of an alkali. This view is further confirmed by our results on the change of electrical conductivity of antimonic acid sol due to ageing (Table XII).

TABLE XII

Sol conc. = 0.95 g./litre.

Date	...	15-8-28	20-8-28	30-8-28	13-9-28
Sp. condy. $\times 10^3$	...	3.06	3.00	3.02	2.98
ρ_n	...	4.2	—	—	4.3

We have observed that the sols of antimonic acid, when coagulated by monovalent electrolytes like KCl, NaCl, can be reconverted into the sol state by washing them with water. These sols therefore, resemble the typical lyophilic sols *e.g.* gelatine, soap, etc. in this respect.

From the Tables IV, VIII and X we observe that the molecular conductivity of the sols of telluric, molybdic and tungstic acids increases with dilution showing that more and more of simple molecules are being formed at the expense of the polymerised molecules and the colloidal particles on dilution. Our experimental results given in Table VI with molybdic acid show that the percentage of colloidal molybdic acid decreases with the increasing dilution of the sol.

It is interesting to note in the following table that the molecular conductivities of LiIO₃, CdCl₂, CdBr₂, CdI₂, and H₂CdI₄, at 18° increase markedly with dilution.

TABLE XIII

Conc.	LiCl.	BaCl ₂ .	LiIO ₃ .	CdCl ₂ .	CdBr ₂ .	CdI ₂ .	H ₂ CdI ₄ .
0.0001 M	98.1	—	66.7	—	—	—	—
0.0005	97.2	117.0	65.9	—	—	—	—
0.001	96.5	115.6	65.3	—	99.0	91.0	204
0.005	93.9	—	62.9	91.0	86.5	76.7	186
0.01	92.1	106.7	61.2	83.0	76.3	65.6	169
0.05	86.1	96.0	55.3	59.0	53.2	40.1	128
0.10	82.4	90.8	51.5	50.0	44.6	31.0	113
0.50	70.7	77.3	39.0	30.8	25.2	18.3	89
1.00	63.4	70.1	31.2	22.4	18.3	15.4	82

The molecular conductivities of LiCl and BaCl₂ have been incorporated in the above table for comparison. It is well known that the cadmium salts and iodates exist partly in the polymerised form in solution, and it is to be concluded from the table that at higher concentrations the polymerised molecules of these salts rapidly increase in number,

In the following table some of the results of Harman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1155) on the equivalent conductivities of sodium silicates are given.

TABLE XIV

	$\nu = 1$	10	100
$\frac{1}{2}$ Na_2SiO_3	85.57	157.5	193
$\frac{1}{2}$ $\text{Na}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5$	81.25	130.8	155
$\frac{1}{2}$ $\text{Na}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_7$	23.24	57.8	81.5

We are of opinion that the rapid change in the equivalent conductivities of the polysilicates $\text{Na}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_7$, on dilution is due to the formation of more of simple anions at the lower concentration of the silicates. Thus

Similar results were obtained by Biltz and Vegesack (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 78, 481) for the equivalent conductivity of the sol of Congo red, which is the sodium salt of a dibasic acid.

TABLE XV

Temperature = 25°

Dilution	... 32	64	128	256	512	1024
Equiv. condy.	... 58.7	64.3	71.0	79.3	87.6	96.1

McBain and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 118, 1279, 1300) have reported that the molecular conductivity of soap solutions at first rapidly decreases then increases to pass through a maximum with increasing concentrations.

DISCUSSION

It is well known that the specific conductivity of well dialysed colloids is slightly greater than that of the water used as a medium (*vide* Walden, "Das Leitvermogen der Losungen", 1924, p. 320). A dialysed sol of silicic acid prepared by Kohlrausch (*Weid. Ann.*, 1893, 50, 133) had the specific conductivity of 11.3×10^{-5} . One of the sols prepared by us by the hydrolysis of silicon tetrachloride gave a specific conductivity of 5.75×10^{-5} at 30°. It is well known that the heat of neutralisation of silicic acid by an alkali is 5230 cal. against H_2S with 7800 cal. and carbonic acid with 20,180 cal., showing that silicic acid is an extremely weak acid. Hence its conductivity due to its acid character is exceedingly small and it is practically impossible to draw any conclusion regarding its state of polymerisation from the electrical conductivity measurements. Telluric acid behaves in the same way as silicic acid. As the inherent electrical conductivity of these sols is so small, ageing, which may cause polymerisation, is not likely to show a decrease in the electrical conductivity but may lead to a small increase in the electrical conductivity due to the release of the adsorbed ions like H^+ , Cl^- etc. and this behaviour has actually been observed with silicic and telluric acid sols. In this respect these sols behave like the sols of ferric hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide etc. On the other hand, the sols of vanadic, molybdic, tungstic and antimonie acids being stronger acids are much more electrically conducting and the effect of ageing on these sols is

chiefly characterised by the polymerisation of the simple molecules causing a decrease in the electrical conductivity with time.

The foregoing observations show that antimonic, vanadic, tungstic and molybdic acids behave like the typical colloidal electrolyte, soap, studied by McBain and co-workers (*loc. cit.*).

It appears, that a colloidal electrolyte is obtained from such a sol, which contains a part of the same substance as ionisable simple and complex molecules. The electrical charge on the colloid particles originates mainly from the adsorption of the complex anion, and the ions obtained from the simple and polymerised molecules are responsible for the high electrical conductivity of the sol. In the case of such sols as those of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_3$, etc. the electrical charge on the colloid particles is due to the preferential adsorption of an ion from an electrolyte, which is an impurity in the sol and can be removed by dialysis. The general scheme of the formation of the two types of colloids is, therefore, identical; in the first case the stabilising electrolyte is obtained from the dissolution of the dispersed particles arising from the same substance; whilst in the second case, the peptising substance is an electrolyte added to or formed in the medium during the formation of the sol. The view advanced in this paper regarding the nature of the colloidal electrolytes forms a part of the micellar theory of the constitution of the colloids as advanced by Pauli and others.

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